

A LOOK AT THE HISTORY OF THE STRUGGLE AGAINST LABOR IN TURKESTAN

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Abstract: This article provides analytical thoughts about the term laborer, the history of labor in Turkestan, and the actions and public protests against it.

Key words: Turkestan, labor, Central Asia, tsarism, metropolis, colony.

The second half of the 19th century was a period when the fate of the peoples of Central Asia took a sharp and tragic turn. As a result of Tsarism's military campaigns in the 60s and 80s of the XIX century, they were included in the new system of legal, political and socio-economic relations that arose and developed in the "foreign country" direction and depending on the Russian Empire. These relations, which were imposed by force, destroyed the traditionally established relations in the region and their opportunities for development on a national basis. The legal formalization of new relations was carried out through the creation of appropriate institutions of power and a management system that worked according to the principle of "metropolis - colony" or "center - foreign country".

Thus, the people of Turkestan were under double oppression from the very beginning. Khanate administrative-tax reserved for them; system was reinforced by the full power of the police-bureaucratic state of the Russian Empire and, in addition, by the methods of national-colonial oppression¹.

In the Middle Ages, Mardikor was called "chairikor" in rural areas, sometimes "mardikor", and only "mardikor" in cities. There were several "Mardikor markets" in every city, district center, and large villages of the country, where hired labor was purchased².

Labor is widespread in our country. Despite having a significant place in the life of the society, it has not become a social class and stratum with an ancient, stable social prestige, status, rights and obligations.

The main reason why the Mardikors were called so by the Russians was that after the initial actions of the government of Tsarist Russia to force the country's population into military work failed, it came up with a new method.

¹ Abduraxmonova N., Ergashev F. Turkistonda Chor mustamlaka tizimi. T. 2002 y. 35-bet.

² Choriyev Z. Turkiston mardikorlari: safarbarlik va uning oqibatlari(1916-1917 yy).T.1999 y. 32-bet.

According to this, local residents of the Turkestan region were mobilized under the guise of assisting in military operations in the territory of Tsarist Russia for a certain period of three months at a fixed daily wage. Consequently, the term "hired workers", i.e. "laborers" was used in relation to the residents of our country who were taken to work for a certain amount of time. But until now, our scientists have been calling the people of Turkestan "workers behind the front" in their works, because they work behind the front.

So, the use of the terms "laborer" and "laborer" in relation to the population of our country, who were mobilized to perform military work in the areas behind the front line and in the areas of the active army during the war, is true. However, at that time, the local population interpreted this mobilization as labor recruitment³.

The great defeats at the front and behind the front, the loss of human, labor and industrial potential, to compensate for these, to recover the regions in the Russian Empire with a difficult situation, to have ready, additional and cheap reserves of labor, without taking into account the backwardness and lack of mental adjustment in Turkestan, to stabilize the situation in the war. , that is, in order to get out of the situation, the tsarist government dared to commit such a criminal act. In the direction of false patriotism, hundreds of thousands of people of Turkestan, who have not adapted to the social, cultural and technological development of Europe neither practically, nor mentally, nor climatically, are sent to sapory, wood cutting, food, fodder, horse-hunting on the front and on the edge of the front where the brutal war is going on. a decree was issued on illegal mobilization for mining, transport, railway work. As a result, this event ended with hundreds of thousands of healthy, able-bodied residents falling ill due to hard work and winter days, most of them perished, and only a small part returned to their country. This was an alleged continuation of the open criminal policy of the tsarist colonial system against our people for fifty years.

In July 1916, the largest national-liberation uprising against colonialism began in Turkestan. Peasants, artisans, and the poor in cities and villages joined the active movement against the local administration, against the recruitment of representatives of the indigenous population to work behind the war. They burned lists of conscripts, beat and sometimes even killed representatives of the authorities, carried out armed attacks on the offices and houses of uezd and bulis managers, and organized skirmishes with the police and the military⁴.

³ Choriyev Z. Turkiston mardikorlari: safarbarlik va uning oqibatlari(1916-1917 yy).T.1999 y. 34-bet

⁴ Abduraxmonova N., Ergashev F. Turkistonda Chor mustamlaka tizimi. T. 2002 y. 139-bet.

The tsarist government, deeply worried by the situation, began to take urgent measures to suppress the uprising. On July 17, 1916, martial law was declared in Turkestan. Mass and disorderly arrests were carried out, and the participants of the uprising were brought to a military court. "Special military courts" were established among the officers of the tsarist army in accordance with the procedure specified in Article 1308 of the Military Court Regulations. In his telegram to the local authorities, the Minister of Defense D. S. Shuvaev instructed these courts to "go to all regions of the country without any hindrance for the immediate consideration of cases related to the insurrection, and as soon as sufficient information is received on "certain persons", without waiting for the investigation of other participants to be completed, the right to sue was given⁵.

The participants of the uprising were prosecuted as criminals under Article 100 of the Criminal Code. He meant the death penalty for the active participants in the uprising. According to this article, most of the participants of the uprising in Jizzakh district were punished.

Trials were held behind closed doors. Tsar's justice would decide the fate of the accused in two or three days at most. Despite the fact that most of the cases consisted of several hundred pages, the indictments were often issued "with lightning speed", as the assistant chief military prosecutor Ignatovich boasted in his letter to the commander of the Turkestan military district. Based on this information, it should be mentioned that the 1916 anti-labor struggle in Turkestan not only represented the will of the people, but was also a harsh result of the unjust policy of the colonial administration and the violation of the rights of the local population everywhere.

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⁵ O'rta Osiyo va Qozog'istondagi 1916 yil qo'zg'oloni. Xujjatlar to'plami (rus tilida). M., 1960, 640-bet.

